

Deliverable 6.2

Website Development

Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
H2020-MSCA-ITN-2014
Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

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Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this task: CITA

Dissemination Level: DEC

R Document, report
DEM Demonstrator, pilot, prototype
DEC Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.
OTHER

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Annex 1 - Innochain Dissemination Plan

Introduction

Deliverable 6.2 presents the planning and execution of Innochain's web based presence. This is organised around 2 central components:

- The external website by which the network communicates and shares information about the network aims, the work packages, the training and evaluation events and the individual ESR research projects to a broad public audience, the industry partners and other interested parties
- Social media platforms including Instagram, Twitter and Facebook

The aim of this deliverable is to describe the overarching aims of the web based dissemination strategy, the corresponding structures of the platforms set in place for its execution and their first content.

The document is supported by the Innochain Dissemination Plan (Annex 1) which outlines the relationship between the web based platforms and the network's further public, scientific and industrial dissemination activities.

The deliverable is structured around three chapters :

- Chapter 1 – A description of Innochain's web based dissemination strategy and its aims, structure and timeframe
- Chapter 2 - An overview of the web-based platforms including their planning and execution
- Chapter 3 - A report on the first 6 months achievements of the Innochain web based dissemination activities.

Chapter 1: Innochain's web based dissemination strategy

The aim for the Innochain web platforms is to disseminate:

- The research questions, methods, experiments and results of the individual ESR research projects and their industrial collaboration
- The research questions, methods, experiments and results of the scientific work packages (WP 3,4 and 5) and their industrial collaboration
- The planning, running and results of research training and evaluation events

It is furthermore the ambition that the Innochain web platforms shall exist as a shared platform by which the broader inter-sector network communicate amongst themselves and to its specialised interest groups. It is therefore important that the platforms also includes community based announcements including updates on ongoing activities, calls for conferences and workshops beyond the network.

It is a central aim that the web based platforms should relate the research activities to a broad public audience, while also communicating scientific results to interested parties in science and industry. As such the web based dissemination strategy addresses the same three target groups identified in the wider dissemination plan (public, scientific and industrial).

The further aim is that Innochain's web based platforms should be democratic with distributed access to dissemination. Where shared content about informing about the network aims, structure and timeframes is edited by the network administrator in collaboration with Dissemination Work Package responsible (Wp 6: IAAC) and in coordination with the supervisory board, further content on the individual ESR research projects and the coordinated efforts of the three scientific work packages is posted throughout the development of each research by the ESRs (the log book) and the work package responsibilities.

The results of Innochain take on many forms, from speculative design probes, and demonstrators to processes and methods, originating from the projects and collaborations, to discussions and novel concepts emerging in workshops, seminars, colloquia and conferences.

The Innochain network aims to include and activate all these levels for dissemination and to provide them with the right tools to create a broad outreach to the target groups.

1.1 A strong graphic identity and the role of image based information

It is the aim that the developed web based platforms should support graphics based information in the form of images, diagrams, models and drawings. The network joins the specialised practices of architecture, engineering and fabrication. These practices have in common a strong graphical training in which drawings and models are the central communicants by which information is shared. The field rely on strong image based information by which to communicate research questions, methods and results.

Innochain has therefore chosen to develop a graphic supporting website in which also further media such as 3D models and video can be supported and has selected social media platforms in which image based information, video and also code can be communicated and shared.

1.2 Structure

The key structure of the web based platforms seek to enable the immediate sharing of research based content. The central web presence is focussed on the Innochain website. This exists as a port of call and main reference for all other platforms. It includes an outline of the network focus, the partnerships and the work packages as well as devoted pages - sub sites - on which the individual ESR projects are continuously logged and updated.

The web site is connected to and supports a select list of social media platforms intended to support the strong graphical identity of the network. Innochain has chosen to focus on the following platforms:

- Twitter, Instagram and Facebook by which to disseminate running network information to a broad audience as well as network followers
- Flickr, Pinterest and Vimeo by which to disseminate, log and store key graphical information in the form of images, diagrams, models and drawings as well as video.
- Github for the sharing, management and co-development of computational code
- Issuu for the sharing of the internal network journal and the extended catalogues that accompany the research exhibitions

1.3 Time frame

The Innochain web based platforms have been built up in a two phase system. In the first phase (from the acceptance of the Grant Agreement (December 2014) and till month 6 (February 2016) the Innochain website was developed as a recruitment platform. Here, central information about the network, its partnership and the 15 ESR positions were posted as a central point of call to which EU, institutional and national recruitment pages pointed.

As Innochain achieved ESR full recruitment (November 2015) we started phase 2 for which the full web site was developed.

1.4 Regular dissemination and updating of web content

The aim for the Innochain web based platform is to have new or renewed information posted continuously during the network period. After the initial setup of the website, in month 6, the goal for the Innochain website is to have, four new or renewed entries on the web site per month. After the initial setup of the social media communication platforms also have individual entry goals (please see table 1 below).

Chapter 2 - An overview of the web-based platforms including their planning and execution

The Innochain web site (Fig.1) <http://www.innochain.net/>) is the central point of call for the network. It presents information about participants, progress and project related events and logs the running progression of the scientific work packages and the individual ESRs.

Fig.1: The startpage of Innochain.net, February 2016.

2.1 Website content

The website provides information about the Innochain network under the following seven categories:

1) Start page:

The start page opens with a strong visual identity. A rotating banner provides news and entry to different areas of the webpage. A short text introduces the mission and vision of the network. Beneficiaries and industry partners are introduced with logos and rollovers, that provide access to the partner section of the Innochain page. The EU emblem and explanation of the funding programme by which Innochain is supported is clearly identified in the page footer, which is always visible.

Further elements are linked to:

- Join our Newsletter tab on the webpage
- A link to the internal webpage of the consortium.
- Link to the social media pages
- Infoboxes on news, upcoming events, social media (integrates the #Innochain and other hashtags of the Innochain participants)
- Live twitter feed of @inno_chain

2) About page

The About page gives a general overview of the Innochain vision and mission as well as the correlated work packages that structure the network activities. Access to all social media channels is also available on this page.

3) Partners page

The partners page introduces the work packages and provides detailed information on the beneficiaries and industry partners with images, contact info and links to the projects they are involved in. It also includes links to the individual partner pages, internal to the innochain.net web domain, so as to not lose visibility.

4) Research Projects page

The Research Projects page provide an overview and entry to the individual research projects, including information on the involved ESR, the beneficiary institution and associated industry partners. It links to the individual ESR sub sites in which each ESR project is continually logged (log books). Images and videos can be embedded through flickr image carousels and vimeo video.

5) Training page

The Training page holds information about upcoming training events, colloquia, conferences - and provides link to journal reports and videos of past events. An embedded google calendar provides an overview of events.

The page invites external parties (PhD's, industry actors and other interested parties) to partake in the open event and provides means to register and sign-up.

6) Dissemination page

The Dissemination page is the central repository for the Innochain related publications (scientific papers, reports, videos etc) and datasets. The dissemination section lists all publications and gives access to their content, via uploaded files (i.e. pdfs) or through referrals to external providers and servers, as well as the Innochain repository on issuu.

7) News page

The news page provides the latest news from the Innochain network and extended partnership including announcement of new entries, as reports, journals, videos on the dissemination page.

2.2 Management of the website

An effective management of the website and the content creation is necessary to disseminate interesting results fast and on a high quality level.

The website is administered by the Innochain network administrator. Her role is to create posts on networks events and dissemination activities, maintain the Innochain calendar of events, monitor the frequency of posts and their compliance with the Innochain publication protocols and she will trigger the creation of posts in periods of too little activity.

Where the Network Administrator in collaboration with the Dissemination Work package responsible (Work Package 6: IAAC) and the Supervisor board edits the core content of website, the right to edit and author web content on innochain.net is given to the scientific work pages responsables and all ESRs in order to have ESRs and partners provide ongoing and up to date information on their project and aggregate in general many entries and diverse voices on the webpage.

2.3 Website protocols

The Innochain webpage has to respect the intellectual rights of Innochain partnership. The management of the Innochain webpage therefore includes an editors protocol so as to check, that published content on the webpage is not harming others intellectual property rights. All published content needs to have a [creative commons zero license](#) or the respective agreement of the author(s) to be published. All published content on the web page needs to provide the full name of the author(s) and institution(s) where developed, the industry partnerships, as well as the name of the Innochain network.

2.4 Innochain Social Media and 3rd party web platforms

Social Media is an effective way to spread news and content to all target groups. Innochain uses the unique tag #Innochain on all entries on social media.

A presence on a range of platforms not only reaches many different target groups, but allows Innochain members to publish through appropriate media channels.

Innochain is present on the following platforms, which addresses different target groups and have different goals:

TABLE 1: Aim and purpose of Innochain's different social media platforms

Platform	Aim	Goal
Twitter	Fast information on results and events https://twitter.com/inno_chain	100 tweets with #Innochain a year current status: 8 tweets

Instagram	Dissemination of the visual appealing and spectacular. The Innochain instagram account shifts weekly to another ESR following the ESR project numbers. https://www.instagram.com/innochain/	150 posts with #Innochain a year current status: 47 posts
Facebook	to address the general public with popular content from Innochain.net https://www.facebook.com/innochain.research	30 posts a year current status: 12 posts
Flickr	a repository for high quality and high-resolution images from the whole project period https://www.flickr.com/photos/innochain/	100 images a year current status: 0 images
Issuu	hold publicly available publications from the network, as the network journal https://issuu.com/innochain	2 publications a year current status: 0 publications
Vimeo	repository for videos made by individual ESR and the network of projects and activities and main Innochain events (workshop seminar, colloquia, exhibitions) https://vimeo.com/innochain	5 videos a year current status: 1 video
Pinterest	to hold and collect and share visual information from the individual researchers https://es.pinterest.com/innochain/	-
Github	Code created within the network is shared through GitHub. This allows for internal collaboration and tracking of the development and communication to and involvement to partners external to the network in writing code. https://github.com/innochain	-

2.5 Management of social media

In order to maintain a sufficient amount of posts from Innochain on social media, Innochain defined, that the network administrator stipulates the use of social media and manages the access to the social media presence of Innochain. If necessary she hands out the password and user information for specific users of the platform to network members in order to raise the dissemination activities.

All members of the network are invited to share the info on the network through their own profiles. They will use in any Innochain related posts the tag #Innochain

Chapter 3 - Reporting the first 6 months of Innochain's web based activity

The innochain.net domain was registered on behalf of the applying consortium in 2014. The originally desired URL innochain.eu was at this time already registered to a third party with no relation to research. The .net suffix seemed however sufficient to carry the message of the research network.

3.1 Webpage during Innochain Recruitment Phase

The consortium created a first version of the webpage after the Grant Agreement was signed. This went online in December 2014 (Fig.2) with the aim to inform the interested public and especially possible ESR candidates about the Innochain network and the calls for the 15 ESR position. In line with this a focus was set on the Introduction of the network beneficiaries and industry partners and their work.

(Fig.2) The Home screen of Innochain.net, November 2014

The full roster of partners and their logos was introduced on an overview page (Fig. 3), which linked to descriptions and the official webpages of all partners.

(Fig. 3) The webpage displayed prominently all partners with their logos

Each ESR position was listed with a short text (in the RESEARCH PROJECTS section of the top menu) and links to the full calls and descriptions of requirements and application procedures both on the Innochain website under the PHD VACANCIES voice in the top menu, as well as on the beneficiaries web pages.

The webpage set on a strong visual appeal with large images of well publicized work developed by each of the beneficiaries involved.

3.2 Webpage - further development after project start

The further development of the webpage is here below treated in each of the seven diverse section.

The main changes made with respect to the 1st phase web page include the implementation of a Start page (prior consisting in the about page); as well as the development of all pages relative to the individual research projects and ESRs.

1) Start page (new content)

The Start page has been completely changed in order to provide a comprehensive overview of the Innochain's projects development through the implementation of interactive content such as:

- Links to all social media channels
- Live news feed from twitter.
- News feed on Network news, which provide users with direct insights into the latest developments within Innochain, such as:
 - The news that one of the Innochain ESRs will be organizing a workshop at Smart Geometry 2016, an international conference started in 2001 as a partnership between Practice, Research and Academia, formed by members

of the world's leading architectural and engineering practices and educational institutions;

- The news that Innochain ESRs at ITKE in Stuttgart are collaborating with Achim Menges and Jan Knippers on the design and fabrication of the Elytra Filament Pavilion.
- News feed on the developments of the ESRs and their research logs, i.e.:
 - Innochain ESRs Dimitrie A. Stefanescu, who pursues his research project ESR 5 Alternate Means To Communicate Measure at UCL London, has released a first software artefact related to Innochain – Speckle.
- Overview of the next upcoming training events, to inform and invite interested PhD students to participate, on i.e.:
 - The Theory of Computation and Technology seminar, to be held in May at the Bartlett in parallel to the SimAUD conference, introducing a range of different theories of computation and technology, each from a different practical, historical or philosophical point of view;
 - The transferrable skills course in academic writing, to be held in Stockholm at the KTH in June and will give research students within the Innochain network the opportunity to critically understand the implications of how they present their work through academic and non-academic writing.
 - The Start Up Seminar on the 7th and 8th of March to be held in Copenhagen, where the ESRs will present the state of advancement of each individual research in front of the beneficiaries, the industrial partners and a select group of external scientists;

(Fig. 4) The start page of innochain.net

2) About page

Further implemented content on the About page (Fig. 5):

- Direct social media links have been implemented for easy access to external content such as videos, images, social media.
- Roster of Innochain partners.

(Fig 5) The About page

3) Partner Pages

Further implemented content:

Academic partner pages now not only contain the bio of each partner institution, but also information relative to:

- Biographies and image references for each of the members of the particular institution involved in the project.
- Biographies and image references for each of the ESRs hosted in that institution
- A short description and image references of each research project hosted in that institution, including keywords for easy understanding and localization for google search engine, improving page ranking
- Links to the involved industrial partners internal Innochain pages.

ABOUT PARTNERS RESEARCH PROJECTS TRAINING NEWS CONTACT

CITA

**CENTRE FOR INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND ARCHITECTURE (CITA),
THE ROYAL DANISH ACADEMY OF FINE ARTS, SCHOOLS OF
ARCHITECTURE, DESIGN AND CONSERVATION**

CITY, COUNTRY
www.cita.aucta.dk

CITA focuses on IT as a tool for design, production and communication within key research areas: Digital Formations, new parametric design tools and their physical counterparts, Building Information Modelling, Computer Aided Design and Computer Aided Manufacture, Behaving Architectures, new programmable materials including nanotechnologies and interactive textiles, Interface Ecologies, real-time modelling, Computer Aided Design and Computer Aided Manufacture, Behaving Architectures, new programmable materials including nanotechnologies and interactive textiles, Interface Ecologies, real-time modelling, interface design and intelligent programming. CITA has a strong track record in initiating and running research projects and networks with international partnerships. In 2011 CITA completed the nationally funded research network Digital Crafting concerning many of Innochain's industrial and academic collaborations. In 2012 Mette Ramsgaard Thomsen was awarded the Danish Council for Independent Research Sapere Aude Advanced Research Grant for elite research at top research level. CITA has a strong international reputation and is a central part of the research community on computation and architecture. In 2011 CITA hosted the core research conference Smart Geometry and in 2015 we will host another central conference Design Modelling Symposium. CITA's research has a strong focus on industry collaboration both nationally and internationally through an established programme of industrial PhDs, consultancy, training and research collaboration. CITA is part of the Royal Danish Academy of Fine Arts, Schools of Architecture, Design and Conservation (ADK) with 250 academic staff and 1700 students at PhD, Masters graduate and Bachelor undergraduate level.

Researchers: Professor Mette Ramsgaard Thomsen, Associate Professor Martin Tamke, Associate Professor Pål Aysen.

PEOPLE

METTE RAMSGAARD THOMSEN
CITA / PROFESSOR

Mette Ramsgaard Thomsen is Associate Professor at the Centre for Information Technology and Architecture (CITA) in Copenhagen. He is pursuing a design led research in the interface and implications of computational design and its materialization. He joined the newly founded research centre CITA in 2006 and shaped its design based research practice. Projects on new design and fabrication for wood and fibre based materials led to a series of research projects and digitally fabricated demonstrators that explore an architectural practice engaged with bespoke materials and behavior. Martin initiated and conducted research projects in the emerging field of digital production in building industry and architectural computation. The research connects academic and industrial partners from architecture and engineering, computer and material science and the crafts. Currently he is involved in the EU Framework 7 project [CITABUILD](#), the Danish funded 4-year [Complex Modelling](#) research project and the [adapt](#)- and [innochain](#) PhD research networks.

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MARTIN TAMKE
CITA / ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR

Mette Ramsgaard Thomsen is Associate Professor at the Centre for Information Technology and Architecture (CITA) in Copenhagen. He is pursuing a design led research in the interface and implications of computational design and its materialization. He joined the newly founded research centre CITA in 2006 and shaped its design based research practice. Projects on new design and fabrication for wood and fibre based materials led to a series of research projects and digitally fabricated demonstrators that explore an architectural practice engaged with bespoke materials and behavior. Martin initiated and conducted research projects in the emerging field of digital production in building industry and architectural computation. The research connects academic and industrial partners from architecture and engineering, computer and material science and the crafts. Currently he is involved in the EU Framework 7 project [CITABUILD](#), the Danish funded 4-year [Complex Modelling](#) research project and the [adapt](#)- and [innochain](#) PhD research networks.

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RESEARCH PROJECTS

ESR1 - DESIGN FOR MANUFACTURE AND ASSEMBLY
Author: Kasper Ax

Industrial Partners: design:production, Blumer Lehmann. One of the central achievements of digital chain is the ability to mass customize building elements creating individual solutions and enabling new kinds of building geometries. While methods for the design and production of customised elements have matured, the planning of assembly procedures remains undeveloped in the building sector - in contrast to for example to product design. [read more](#)

Keywords: [Design for manufacture and assembly](#) - [Mass Customisation](#) - [timber](#)

ESR2 - INTEGRATING MATERIAL PERFORMANCE
Author: Tom Svilene

Industrial Partners: Blumer Lehmann, White. The ability to simulate material performance, parametrising and calculating material properties as design drivers present new perspectives in structural and material thinking. By understanding materials not as static or inanimate, but as engaged by complex behaviours, material performance is regarded as one of the richest sources of innovation. New structural paradigms are emerging that integrate material performance such as active bending. [read more](#)

Keywords: [Computational](#) - [INTEGRATING MATERIAL PERFORMANCE](#) - [timber](#)

ESR3 - MULTI-SCALE MODELLING FOR BUILDING DESIGN
Author: Paul Poinet

Industrial Partners: Buro Happold, design:production. Investigating multi-scale modelling principles for architectural design. Multi-scale modelling is an interdisciplinary research topic in which systems are modelled at multiple scales and interfaced enabling the modelling of low scale systems to parametrise and inform high scale systems. The project investigates multi-scale modelling as a means to support iterative build-up of knowledge in the design process in which highly specified material simulations interface with open ended design models. [read more](#)

Keywords: [Multi Scale Modelling](#) - [simulation](#) - [timber](#)

PARTNERS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska Curie grant agreement No. 101019718

(Fig 6) An example of an Innochain partners page

4) Industry partners pages

New Content (prior linked directly to external partner website)

- Industrial partner bio, logo and official website link
- Biographies and image references for each of the members of the particular institution involved in the project.
- A short description and image references of each research project hosted in that institution, including keywords for easy understanding and localization for google search engine, improving page ranking
- Links to the involved academic partners internal Innochain pages.

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HE NN **HENN GMBH**

MÜNCHEN / BERLIN, GERMANY
<http://www.henn.com/en/it>

HENN is an international architecture office with offices in Munich, Berlin and Beijing and 65 years of expertise in the fields of culture and office buildings, teaching and research as well as development, production and masterplanning.

The office is led by Gunter Henn and fourteen partners, 350 employees – architects, designers, planners and engineers – from 25 countries are able to draw upon a wealth of knowledge collected over three generations of building experience in addition to a worldwide network of partners and experts in a variety of disciplines. This continuity, coupled with progressive design approaches and methods and interdisciplinary research projects, forms the basis for a continual examination of current issues and for a consistent design philosophy. Forms and spaces are no mere objective, they are developed from the processes, demands and cultural contexts of each project. As a general contractor we are able to satisfy this principle at every stage of project planning and implementation.

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PEOPLE

MARTIN HENN
HENN / DIPL. ARCH ETH & M.S. A.D.

Martin Henn studied architecture at the University of Stuttgart and at the ETH, Zurich. He received his Master's Degree in Architecture from the ETH, Zurich in 2006, and his Post-Professional Master of Advanced Architectural Design from Columbia University, New York in 2008. Prior to HENN, he was working for Zaha Hadid Architects in London and Asymptote Architecture in New York.
Martin... [read more](#)

MORITZ FLEISCHMANN
HENN / PROFESSOR / RESEARCH CONSULTANT AT HENN

Moritz Fleischmann is a professor for computational design at the Hochschule Düsseldorf (HSD). His research investigates the impact of computer technology on early design stages and transdisciplinary collaborations in architecture. He has published widely and held lectures at conferences around the globe. Besides the university, he is a research consultant for the industry. AT HENN, he organizes the Design Research Exchange (DRX)... [read more](#)

DIMITRIE A. STEFANESCU
UCL /

Dimitrie is a maker of tools, architect, designer and programmer. He is finding and speculating new overlaps between the web, code and design challenges. His main current focus is creating digital design-communication interfaces that enable the collaborative definition of value for all the stakeholders involved in the design process.

innochain

This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska Curie grant agreement No 101019717

(Fig 7) The Industry Partners page

5) Research Projects page

Further implemented content - The page design has been changed to enhance visibility for each of the 3 Work packages: Communicating design, simulation for design and materialising design.

- A small introduction through text and graphic content has been implemented for each Work Package (referred to as *research areas*), which then links to an overview page of that specific Work package
- Below each Work package description links are provided to go to each ESRs log book page, so as to directly follow the research development.

The programme is a new research collaboration established on existing associations and includes 6 academic beneficiaries and 14 industry partners. The relatively large number of industrial partners enables the network to comprise the central design-active stakeholders of building practice reflecting different disciplines as well as different scales of enterprise. The scientific content is structured around 3 work packages (WPs), that creates a cross-site and inter-disciplinary research environment examining the three axes design communication, design simulation and design materialisation in which the 15 ESRs' research is situated.

RESEARCH AREAS

COMMUNICATING DESIGN

Current methods for communicating domain specific knowledge in building practice assume disciplinary separation and discretisation of design control. [More info](#)

- [ESR4 – MULTI-CRITERIA OPTIMISATION IN EARLY DESIGN PHASE](#)
- [ESR3 – INTEGRATING BUILDING PHYSICS FOR PERFORMANCE CONTROL](#)
- [ESR5 – INTEGRATING MATERIAL PERFORMANCE](#)

SIMULATION FOR DESIGN

Current methods for simulation assume single scale engagement across separate phases and exclude the simulation of material and fabrication processes. [More info](#)

- [ESR9 – SIMULATING CONCRETE FORMWORK](#)
- [ESR8 – VIRTUAL PROTOTYPING FRP](#)
- [ESR7 – SIMULATING ANISOTROPIC MATERIAL](#)
- [ESR6 – MULTI SCALAR MODELLING FOR](#)

MATERIALISING DESIGN

Current methods for materialisation within the building industry are based on mass production. They rely on the standardisation of material and fabrication to afford control and optimise material use. [More info](#)

- [ESR15 – SMALL SCALE ROBOTIC MANUFACTURING FOR THE LARGE SCALE BUILDINGS](#)
- [ESR14 – DESIGN FOR MANUFACTURE AND ASSEMBLY](#)
- [ESR13 – APPLIED ROBOTICS](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101019718

(Fig 8) The Research Projects page provides an overview of the ESR and the Workpackages they are related to.

5.1 Individual ESR research project page (in this document also referred to as the log book)

In february 2016 all ESRs attended an Innochain webinar informing them how to develop and post content to their individual sub sites. In early March 2016 as part of the Start Up seminar, the ESRs are expected to have started their sub sites (Fig. 9) and developed the first introductory information and posts (Fig. 10) for each project. New posts by ESRs are automatically displayed in Research Project section of the Innochain Start page.

innochain ABOUT PARTNERS RESEARCH PROJECTS TRAINING NEWS CONTACT

ESR06- MULTI SCALAR MODELLING FOR BUILDING DESIGN

ESR: PAUL POINET
ESR NUMBER: ESR6
INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: [BURO HAPPOLD](#) • [DESIGN2PRODUCTION](#)
INSTITUTE: [CITA](#)

DESCRIPTION:
Investigating multi scale modelling principles for architectural design. Multi-scale modelling is an interdisciplinary research topic in which systems are modelled at multiple scales and interfaced enabling the modelling of low scale systems to parametrise and inform high scale systems. The project investigate multi scalar modelling as a means to support iterative build-up of knowledge in the design process in which highly specified material simulations interface with open ended design modes. Using timber (sustainable and renewable material resource) the project will examine how simulating material performance at low level can be used to inform structural performance at high level. The project is highly interdisciplinary and uses event based simulation frameworks from mathematics, computer science and engineering to analyse and interface domain specific knowledge.

PAUL POINET
CITA / ESR06
Paul Poinet is holding a B.Arch. from the Ecole Nationale Supérieure d'Architecture Paris-Malaquais (ENSAPM) and a M.Sc. in Integrative Technologies and Architectural Design Research from the University of Stuttgart (ICD/ITKE). During his Bachelor of Architecture (2010-2013), he has been working in the design development of concrete lattices at EZCT Architecture & Design Research (Paris) and was involved as a... [read more](#)

POSTS

ADAPTIVE BLANK TYPOLOGIES FOR FREE FORM TIMBERS - ESR6
Author: Paul Poinet
ESR6 - MULTI SCALAR MODELLING FOR BUILDING DESIGN. AUTHOR: Paul Poinet. Multi Scalar Modelling for Building Design (ESR 6). Adaptive blank typologies for free form timbers. from Innochain Research on Vimeso. Based on waste percentage, this algorithm finds the most suitable blank topology for a given free form glue-laminated timber beam. Five... [read more](#)
Keywords: [Design2Production](#), [Freeform Surface](#), [Timber](#)

GRAPH THEORY AND MAPPING SYSTEMS - ESR6
Author: Paul Poinet
ESR6 - MULTI SCALAR MODELLING FOR BUILDING DESIGN. AUTHOR: Paul Poinet. The information data contained within an architectural project is usually increasing proportionally with time. At the beginning of the design process, it is possible manipulate data in a very flexible manner and observe what the design possibilities are according to different... [read more](#)
Keywords:

CATEGORIES CITA | ESR6 | PEOPLE

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(Fig 9) Example of an ESR subpage with two posts.

ADAPTIVE BLANK TYPOLOGIES FOR FREE FORM TIMBERS – ESR6

ESR6 – MULTI SCALAR MODELLING FOR BUILDING DESIGN

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Multi Scalar Modelling for Building Design (ESR 6): Adaptive blank typologies for free form timbers, from innochain Research on Vimeo.

Based on waste percentage, this algorithm finds the most suitable blank topology for a given free form glue-laminated timber beam. Five different typologies are identified: straight, single curved arc, single curved, double curved and double curved with torsion. Each beam can be segmented based on local curvature and/or torsion. The resulted segments can then be analyzed in order to find the most suitable corresponding blank. This research is based on the methods used at [designtoproduction](#) for geometrical rationalization of large scale timber architectural projects.

CATEGORIES | BURUHAPPOLD | CITA | DP | ESR6 | SIMULATION FOR DESIGN

TAGS | DESIGN2PRODUCTION | FREEFORM SURFACE | TIMBER

(Fig 10) Example of ESR Post. these inform about projects and activities the ESR is engaged in and can contain multiple types of media, such as Slide-shows of images, Video, embedded pdfs.

6) Training page

Along with the planning of the semester of training events the Training web pages (Fig. 11) outlining the planning, content and timing of the training events have been posted. The overview page introduces the different types of training activities in Innochain and announces the current and past events individually. These are displayed with a short text and Thumbnail and link to a more extensive page for each individual event (Fig. 12). Upcoming Training events are in the same way displayed on the respective NEWS area of the Innochain start page.

innochain ABOUT PARTNERS RESEARCH PROJECTS TRAINING NEWS CONTACT

TRAINING

To support and advance interdisciplinary and inter-sector collaboration in building practice, the programme approach is to create an interdisciplinary research training environment with a structured secondment programme that allows young researchers to be part of and exposed to a multitude of different academic and industrial research cultures. The programme is interdisciplinary in two ways:

- Through academic training activities that allow young researchers to skill up in both architectural and engineering fields.
- Through the industry participation and secondment programme that includes partners from the four fields of architecture, engineering, design software development and fabrication and which will expose researchers to the applied reality of situated research and development across the digital chain.

The two structures will give young researchers the opportunity to develop new skills that sit across architecture and engineering and to implement and test those in context with leading industry support.

The network training activities are central instruments in forming this platform. It is through training that ESFRs are qualified, partners are assembled, exchange is created and synergy is achieved.

All interested external PhD students and junior researchers are encouraged to participate in the courses. They are free but you need to register in advance.

UPCOMING EVENTS

Training	Training	Training
 START-UP SEMINAR 07/03/2016		
7 - 10 June, 2016. Participation online or in person at KTH Stockholm. This writing seminar will give research students writing... read more	19 - 20 May, 2016 at Bartlett School of Architecture, London. This course introduces a range of different theories... read more	7 - 8 March, 2016 at CITA/KADK, Copenhagen. The aim for the Innochain start up seminar is to create... read more

(Fig 11) Training Overview Page

The individual Training Event pages provide information on the content and organisers of the Training event and invite external PhDs.

The screenshot shows the INNOCHAIN website header with navigation links: ABOUT, PARTNERS, RESEARCH PROJECTS, TRAINING, NEWS, CONTACT. The main heading is "ACADEMIC WRITING - COMING TO WRITING". Below it, the text reads: "TRANSFERABLE SKILLS COURSE", "7-10 JUNE, 2016", "PARTICIPATION ONLINE OR IN PERSON IN STOCKHOLM", "3 ECTS", and "COURSE INSTRUCTOR: ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR HELENE FRICHOT, KTH SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE, STOCKHOLM". A link for "INFORMATION & REGISTRATION" is provided. A photograph of a modern building with a curved facade is shown. Below the photo, there is a paragraph of text explaining the seminar's purpose: "This writing seminar will give research students within the INNOCHAIN network the opportunity to critically understand the implications of how they present their work through academic and non-academic writing. Students will be encouraged to extend their practice of writing beyond the conventional academic norm that is supposed to objectively and transparently account for a research problem. The tasks and exercises we will undertake in this seminar will offer alternative approaches to writing, commencing from the idea that writing is a practice that needs to be developed in critical and creative alignment with the content of a research project." Another paragraph follows: "To develop an understanding of the structure and patterns of academic, scientific and engineering research articles, to improve proficiency in writing scientific articles, and scientific writing in English. Written material will be peer reviewed. Class preparation includes analysis of the texts in the course material and exercises focusing on problematic areas for academic writing for scientists and engineers." A final line of text states: "Each day of the intensive writing seminar will feature a workshop based around a writing task. These tasks will be taken as experiments that aim to explore other ways of..."

(Fig 12) Example of Training Event page

6 Dissemination page

The screenshot shows the INNOCHAIN website dissemination page. The header is identical to the previous page. The main image is a photograph of a large, complex, perforated metal structure, possibly a model or a piece of art, with the text "INNOCHAIN DISSEMINATION" overlaid. Below the image, there are two sections of content. The first section is dated "12/02/2016" and is under the category "Reports". It features a thumbnail image of a document and the title "TRAINING MANAGEMENT PLAN" by "Author: Innochain". The text below reads: "This document serves as a basic introduction to Innochain and aims to guide Innochain ESRs through the project, the collaborations and the training programme. [read report](#)". The second section is dated "07/01/2016" and is under the category "Projects". It features a thumbnail image of a network diagram and the title "PRIVATE EXAMPLE POST" by "Author: Innochain". The text below reads: "The science fair project abstract appears at the beginning of the report as well as on your display board. [read report](#)". At the bottom of the page, there is a footer with the INNOCHAIN logo, a small upward-pointing arrow, and a funding notice: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska Curie grant agreement No 842877". The European Union flag logo is also present.

(Fig 13) Dissemination page

Dissemination represents the efforts of the network as a whole as well as each of the individual ESRs in disseminating the research developed, hence serving as a repository for the network in the web based platform. The content has been divided thanks to a category system, allowing the user to understand the typology of content, and visualizing it consequently according to interest (the default visualization is according to the latest published dissemination article). The categories are: Scientific Papers, Projects, Reports, Journals, Datasets, Codes; allowing to cater for all materials produced by the network.

7) News

(Fig 14) News page

Further implemented content:

The news section is presented in image tile format giving visual content as the first input. Each tile is interactive and leads to the content related post of the news in question. The news can be visualized as a general feed of all news related items, or can be divided according to content tags: Innochain (for network news), Events (for training news), Communicating Design, Simulation for Design and Materializing Design (for the related to the 3 work packages).

3.3 Social Media

The Innochain consortium registered presence for Innochain on the intended platforms before or shortly after the project start.

3.3.1 Facebook

A focus was set on facebook (Fig. 15) and instagram (Fig. 16), as these seemed suited to address a broad audience in a phase of the project where specific research outcome is not mature for scientific publication, but already in a stage which suits visual media.

The first activities on the Innochain facebook page introduced each of the beneficiaries individually and each industry partners. Parallel posts inform about activities of the ESRs, such as the cluster they organise at the Smart Geometry 2016 in Gothenburg; as well as promoting the other social media platforms transversally

(Fig. 15) The Innochain facebook page in January 2016.

3.3.2 Instagram

The Innochain Instagram account is used to provide insights into the research activities, training activities, but as well daily life life of the ESRs at their beneficiaries and the hosting universities and cities, during visits and secondments with their industry partners and dissemination activities. The Innochain instagram account is given every week to another Innochain ESR.

(Fig. 16) The Instagram rotation of ESRs was started in January 2016.

3.4 First achievements

The impact of the social media platforms (facebook and instagram) has been evaluated through statistics of the individual platforms. These results reflect the first month of activity.

3.4.1 Innochain Facebook

The Innochain facebook page ¹went online on the 12th of January 2016.

The current status of the page is as follows:

- 270 page likes aggregated over the period of only two month (Fig. 17)
- 12 posts published

(Fig. 17) Development of likes for the Innochain Facebook page

The most performative post has reached 2.4K, and the most liked post received 210 likes (Fig.18).

¹ <https://www.facebook.com/innochain.research>

		Reach: Organic / Paid		Post Clicks		Reactions, Comments & Shares			
Published	Post	Type	Targeting	Reach		Engagement		Promote	
02/29/2016 12:11 pm	Meet the #Industrial Partners of the #innochain network: Foster			44		3 4		Boost Post	
02/22/2016 12:54 pm	Keep up to date on the #innochain research, check out our inst			2.4K		141 23		Boost Post	
02/08/2016 11:40 am	Meet the #Academic Partners of the #innochain network: KTH Ro			250		8 9		Boost Post	
02/03/2016 5:37 pm	Meet the #Academic Partners of the #innochain network: IoA, Ins			130		8 3		Boost Post	
02/03/2016 12:02 pm	The IaaC<Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia #Innoc			250		9 4		Boost Post	
02/01/2016 11:52 am	Meet the #Academic Partners of the #innochain network: itke bas			581		67 19		Boost Post	
01/27/2016 4:47 pm	Meet the #Academic partners of the #innochain network: Bartlett			154		18 7		Boost Post	
01/25/2016 11:00 am	Meet the #Academic Partners of the #innochain network: IaaC<In			1.1K		210 37		Boost Post	
01/20/2016 4:20 pm	Meet the #Academic Partners of the #innochain network: CITA fo			150		16 8		Boost Post	
01/12/2016 7:05 pm	InnoChain's cover photo			0		59 4		Boost Post	
01/12/2016 7:00 pm	The InnoChain ETN network is a shared research training enviro			1.3K		74 13		Boost Post	
01/08/2016 3:25 pm	InnoChain			0		22 0		Boost Post	

(Fig. 18) An overview of the Innochain Facebook posts and their reach.

3.4.2 Innochain on Instagram

The Instagram page² was created on 12. January 2016.

To date the account has rotated between 4 ESRs together creating 47 posts (Fig. 17). The account boasts 188 followers and is following 765 instagram accounts. Content on the page includes both static and motion media.

The most liked post has 22 likes, and the most commented post has 3 comments.

² <https://www.instagram.com/innochain/>

Annex 1 - Innochain Dissemination & Data Management Plan

Dissemination & Data Management Plan

Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
H2020-MSCA-ITN-2014
Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

Project no.: 642877
Project acronym: InnoChain
Project title: Building Innovation in the Extended Digital Chain

Start date of the project: 01/09/2015
Duration of the project: 48 months

Workpackage: 6 - Dissemination
Task: 6.1
Revision Date of this Deliverable: 22/01/2016

Authors: Martin Tamke (CITA), Mathilde Marengo (IAAC)

Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this task: IAAC

Dissemination Level: Other

R Document, report
DEM Demonstrator, pilot, prototype
DEC Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.
OTHER

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4 Appendix 1: Research exhibition plan

5 Appendix 2: Public Event Plan

6 Appendix 3: Publication Plan

1.1 Introduction

1.1 Objective and structure

Part of the objective of Work Package 6 is to define the tools and processes through which information about the project is communicated to building industry, the scientific community and the general public. This document is to specify the necessary plan, that will guide the project's dissemination strategy and actions.

The essential parts of the plan are: what will be disseminated, who is the intended audience, what is the dissemination method and associated tools, and finally, when each activity will take place.

The plan provides for each dissemination tool protocols, to implement the dissemination aims and goals, and measures to evaluate the success of the dissemination activities.

1.2 Dissemination approach

Dissemination aims to spread research results and to promote the research ideas. It aims simultaneously to invite third parties to comment, participate and collaborate.

The Innochain network produces on all levels results, which can be disseminated. They originate from:

- work and collaboration of the individual ESR
- hosting beneficiary
- industrial collaborators
- the level of the network itself.

The results of Innochain take on many forms, from speculative design probes, and demonstrators to processes and methods, originating from the projects and collaborations, to discussions and novel concepts emerging in workshops, seminars, colloquia and conferences.

The Innochain network aims to include and activate all these levels for dissemination and to provide them with the right tools to create a broad outreach to the target groups.

1.3 Target groups

The dissemination is structured around three key target groups:

- Public (including civil society and media)
- Scientific
- Industry (including customers)

The Innochain network has a strong international inter-sector profile. Activating all partners to disseminate in their local environments and communities allows to reach out to the many levels of industry and academia - from design oriented architectural offices, to engineering firms, computational design communities and fabricators to the general public in many European regions.

Strong visuals and narratives are an important part of dissemination to all key target groups. The creation of images and videos is implemented on all levels of dissemination activities.

1.4 General dissemination and data management protocol

All results of Innochain should be published. All publication should adhere to the IPR agreement and protocols.

The Grant Agreement §29 DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS — OPEN ACCESS — VISIBILITY OF EU FUNDING describes in detail this general obligation to disseminate scientific results and prescribes as well procedures to inform involved network beneficiaries and industry partners about the intent to disseminate 45 days before publication and the right of other beneficiaries to object within 30 days of receiving this notification.

In Innochain the information about upcoming dissemination activities takes place within the monthly management meetings and are documented in the meetings minutes. Possible objections are to be raised via email to the network administrator and the concerned beneficiary.

Innochain is taking part in the [Horizon 2020 Pilot on Open Research Data](#) and will give the same amount of attention in publishing the research results underlying datasets, as to the publication of the research results itself.

2 Project Identity

A common reference identity in all dissemination tasks allows for better visibility and recognition as well as branding of the project. Furthermore, as also required by §29.4 of the grant agreement, all publications and presentations by members of Innochain consortium - including all ESR - must acknowledge the EU financial support received.

All dissemination tools and activities refer to the name of the project, to the project's website URL and to the graphic elements described in this section.

2.1 Innochain Logo

2.2 EU Emblem

Rules for the use of the emblem and download links can be found here:
http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/communication/services/visual_identity/index_en.htm

2.3 Templates for dissemination

The network develops a coherent identity through the engagement of an external graphic designer for the core publications of the network. The internal communication platform of Innochain will distribute templates for:

- Innochain network journal
- exhibition catalogues [example](#)

- event announcements in web (flyer) and print format ([example](#))
- info flyers on the general Innochain network
- info booklets for events [example](#)
- way finding signs for events

The internal communication platform will as well hold templates made from best practice of dissemination activities, which emerge during the network's operation, such as videos.

2.4 General publication protocol (Project identity)

Unless it is impossible or the Innochain Supervisor board agrees any result and dissemination document or action must:

- Display the Innochain and EU emblem with appropriate prominence and balance to each other and eventually other displayed emblems
- Refer to the project's website URL www.Innochain.net
- Show the following text:
 "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 642877"

3 Dissemination tools

The network focusses on innovation in practice. This means that innovation is not limited to technological innovation but also includes the innovative potential of implementing known tools and processes to create new products and solutions. This requires dissemination tools, which are able to transport results as well as process and context of the conducted research.

The project emphasises tools that allow for engagement of the addressed target groups. It develops tools, which have the potential to address all groups simultaneously, as website or social media, and more targeted dissemination tools for public, scientific and industry dissemination.

3.1 Public Dissemination

Public dissemination aims to expose the broader public to the research questions, methods and results. The aim is here to invite non-specialists into the research context and communicate the overall aims of the network, the interdisciplinary breadth and the unique synergy enabled through the programme.

Innochain plans to establish the following activities. Additional public dissemination activities are expected to emerge throughout the project period, as for instance a public display in a gallery setting of the results of the Summer school in Berlin in project month 16.

3.1.1 Research exhibition

The research exhibition presents the material research undertaken as part of the research investigations. Research can often be alienating in its complexity. The gallery setting invites the public to experience experimental results presented as physical building experiments. The network plans three research exhibitions with each their scalar focus (Speculative Design Probes, Material Prototypes and Demonstrators). The research exhibition happen in parallel to the main scientific-evaluative research events (the two colloquia and the final international conference) that also are open for public participation.

Exhibition	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
First year Exhibition "Design Probes"	IOA	18
Second year Exhibition "Prototypes"	KTH	30
Final exhibition "Demonstrators"	CITA	45

3.1.2 Website

<http://www.innochain.net/> is the central point of information on the project, its participants, progress and project related events. the webpage invites to participate and promotes the ideas of the network.

The web based blog continually disseminates the research events (colloquia, workshop-seminars and the final international conference) and each ESR will have an own project page on to which development on his/her project is logged. It acts as a means of communicating the network programme and posting the research results.

3.1.2.1 Website content

The website provides complete information on the network in the following categories:

Start page with strong visual identity. A rotating banner provides news and entry to different areas of the webpage. A short text introduces mission and vision of the network. The partners are introduced with images and rollovers, which provide access to the partner section of the page. Further elements:

- Join our Newsletter tab on the webpage
- A link to the internal webpage of the consortium.
- Link to the social media pages
- infoboxes on news, upcoming events, social media (integrates the #Innochain and other hashtags of the innochain participants)

About - gives general overview, vision and mission, work packages

Partners - introduces the work packages and provides detailed information on the partners with images, contact info and links to the projects, they are involved in, as their individual webpages

Projects and ESR - Provide an overview and entry to the individual research projects, including information on the involved ESR and partners and the ESR log books. Images and videos can as well be embedded through flickr image carousels and vimeo video.

Events & Training - shows upcoming training events, colloquia, conferences - and provides link to reports, videos etc. of past events. An embedded google calendar provides an overview. The page invites external parties to partake and provides means to register and sign-up.

Dissemination - the website is the central repository for the Innochain related publications (scientific papers, reports, videos etc) and datasets. The dissemination section lists all publications and gives access to their content, via uploaded files (i.e. pdfs) or through referrals to external providers and servers.

News - latest news from the network and extended partnership, announcement of new entries, as reports, journals, videos on the page.

The goal for www.innochain.net is to have, after the initial setup of the website, four new or renewed entries on the webpage per month.

3.1.2.2 Management of the website

The website is administered by the Innochain network administrator. His/her role is to create posts on networks events and dissemination activities, maintain the Innochain calendar of events, monitor the frequency of posts and their compliance with the Innochain publication protocols. He/she triggers the creation of posts in case of too little activity.

The rights to edit and author web content on innochain.net can furthermore be given to any member of the network in order to have ESRs and partners provide info on their project and aggregate in general many entries and diverse voices on the webpage.

3.1.2.3 Website protocols

All published content on the webpage may not harm others intellectual rights and needs to have a [creative commons zero license](#) or the respective agreement of the author(s) to be published. All published content on the web page needs to provide the full name of the author(s) and institution(s) where developed, the industry partnerships, as well as the name of the Network.

3.1.3 Social Media and 3rd party web platforms

Social Media is an effective way to spread news and content into all target groups. Innochain uses the unique tag #innochain on all entries on social media.

A presence on a range of platform addresses not only reaches many different target groups, but allows Innochain members to publish through appropriate channels.

Innochain is present on the following platforms, which addresses different target groups and have different goals:

Platform	Aim	Goal
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Twitter	fast information on results and events	100 tweets with #innochain a year
Instagram	Dissemination of the visual appealing and spectacular. The Innochain instagram account shifts weekly to another ESR following the ESR project numbers.	150 posts with #innochain a year
Facebook	to address the general public with popular content from Innochain.net	30 posts a year
Flickr	a repository for high quality and high-resolution images from the whole project period	100 images a year
Issuu	hold publicly available publications from the network, as the network journal	2 publications a year
Vimeo	repository for videos made by individual ESR and the network of projects and activities and main Innochain events (workshop seminar, colloquia, exhibitions)	5 videos a year
Pinterest	to hold and collect and share visual information from the individual researchers	-
Github	Code created within the network is shared through GitHub. This allows for internal collaboration and tracking of the development and communication to and involvement to partners external to the network in writing code.	-

3.1.3.1 Management of social media

The network administrator stipulates the use of social media and manages the access to the social media presence of Innochain. If necessary he/she hands out the password and user information for specific users of the platform to network members in order to raise the dissemination activities.

All members of the network are invited to share the info on the network through their own profiles. They will use in any Innochain related posts the tag #innochain

3.1.3.2 Social Media and popular web platforms protocols

The #innochain tag must be used in all publications on Social Media and popular web platforms.

3.1.4 Newsletters

Innochain will establish a newsletter which informs about the release of the network journal, upcoming events and news from within the Innochain partnership including ESR, beneficiaries and industry partners.

The mailing list will be organised through mailchimp. Each beneficiary will provide a list of mail contacts. Industry partners will be invited to contribute. A “Join our Newsletter tab” on the webpage provides interested persons a possibility to opt in.

The goal is to have a newsletter every 6 month.

3.1.4.1 Management of the newsletter

The network administrator will collect the news for the newsletter and prepare and execute the posting with the leaders

3.1.6 Extended catalogue

The extended catalogue is issued after the final exhibition and international conference of the network. It disseminates the results to a wider audience of interested public, architecture practitioners, students and researchers alike. It is a durable record in which network researchers (practice and academia), ESRs and invited researchers partaking are asked to contribute with critically reflecting texts.

The catalogue is issued electronically and on print and follows established formats, such as the [Digital Crafting research](#) extended catalogue by CITA.

	Main topic	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	Extended Catalogue	CITA	45

3.1.6.1 Innochain extended catalogue management and protocols

CITA is responsible for the extended catalogue and will develop it in collaboration with the workpackage 6 lead, the network administrator and the further Innochain partnership.

3.1.5 Outreach activities to local environments, external web portals & communities

The Innochain network and its members will multiply the outreach through the dissemination of events, results and news on external platforms (as. www.cultureagora.info), the local environments (as the beneficiaries webpages and calendars) and related communities (as. www.grasshopper3d.com).

This public outreach activities will include:

- presenting research to school and A level students
- developing themed workshops with bachelor and masters students
- participating in public dissemination event such as The Festival of Research, DK, European Researchers Night (UK) and Lange Nacht der Wissenschaften (DE)

3.1.7.1 Outreach management and protocols

Beneficiaries organising outreach activities will inform the network administrator in due time, who will post these on the Innochain webpage and relevant other dissemination channels.

Information and invitation on all overall network events of Innochain will be send in due time in electronic form through the network administrator to the beneficiaries and industry partners. These will implement protocols on their end to publish these events on their web platforms. They will provide the network administrator with contact data to send the event information to.

The network administrator will establish with the help of the network a list of relevant external platforms notify these in due time about upcoming Innochain events and news.

All posts have to link to the original page or the home page of www.Innochain.net

3.2 Scientific Dissemination

Scientific dissemination aims to share and critically discuss research at the highest scientific level. The scientific dissemination is further divided into internal and external dissemination:

Internal dissemination - shares and evaluates research results runningly so as to support synergy and critically engage in each other's research questions, method and results. Internal events centre on the evaluative research events (colloquia and pre-viva seminar) as well as the hands-on workshops (as part of the workshop-seminars). The internal events have a network focus but are open to the public from which we expect participation from an audience of specialists and researchers from practice and academia as well as research students.

External dissemination aims to make research results part of the larger scientific arena. Its core focus lies with progressively publishing of results in key scientific conference and journals.

The scientific dissemination tools are in detail:

3.2.1 Publication in international conferences, workshops and journals

Research results will be progressively published in key international research conferences, such as:

ACADIA, Advances in Architectural Geometry, Design Modelling Symposium, RobArch, Fabricate, IASS, IABSE (international association for bridge and structural engineering) and eCAADe

and journals such as:

IJAC (International Journal of Architecture and Computation) or IJSS (International Journal of Shell and Spatial Structures)

The goal is to have three scientific publications per year per scientific work package in a conference, workshop or journal external to the network.

3.2.2 Colloquia and Pre-Viva seminar

The two colloquia act as evaluation events in which research progress is assessed and scientific quality assured. The colloquia and pre-viva seminars are open events and also act as scientific dissemination to a wider scientific audience.

	Colloquium	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	First year Colloquium & Exhibition "Design Probes"	IOA	18
2	Second year Colloquium & Exhibition "Prototypes"	IAAC	30

3.2.2.1 Colloquia and Pre-Viva seminar protocols

The Colloquia and Pre-Viva seminar are organised by a dedicated beneficiary in collaboration with the network administrator. Together they are inviting the public through broadly spread announcements on the web, flyers etc. The organising beneficiary is responsible for the documentation on event with good quality photo and video. The events will be reported via articles in the Innochain network journal, photo galleries and video on the web platforms of Innochain.

The ESR are asked to prepare 1 - 2 minute long videos of project progress for every colloquium. These videos will be put online before, during or after the event.

3.2.2.2 Final ESR report

The final ESR reports document on a scientific level the individual research projects conducted by the Innochain Early Researchers. They provide profound insights into the project's underlying research questions, related state of the art, the chosen method, the process and results of the work.

The ESR reports are shared with the public through the Innochain webpage.

3.2.3 Innochain workshops

The workshops are open events inviting researches and PhD fellows from beyond the network to participate in the hands-on learning environment. As such they act as scientific dissemination events that enable outreach and the sharing of methods and tools.

	Workshop	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	Workshop-seminar 1.1 Communication design	CITA	12
2	Workshop-seminar 1.2 Simulating design	ITKE	12
3	Workshop-seminar 1.3 Materialising design	BSA	12
4	Workshop-seminar 2.1 Communicating design	KTH	24
5	Workshop-seminar 2.2 Simulating design	IOA	24
6	Workshop-seminar 2.3 Materialising design	IAAC	24

3.2.3.1 Innochain workshop protocols

The workshops are organised by appointed beneficiaries. The workshops have a network focus but are open to the public of specialists and researchers from practice and academia as well as research students. The organising beneficiary will in collaboration with the network administrator invite to the workshops via the web, flyers, local platforms etc.

The organising beneficiary is responsible for the documentation on event with good quality photography and video and the publication of these on www.innochain.net and the other Innochain web platforms.

The 6 workshops will be documented in the Innochain network journal.

3.2.4 Innochain Conference

The network will conclude in a large scale international conference with peer reviewed paper presentations from the field.

Conference	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
Concluding international conference	CITA	45

3.2.5 Innochain network journal

The Innochain network journal aims to disseminate results to a wider audience of researchers, architectural practitioners, students and the interested public alike.

The format of an electronic journal is well known to the network, as in the [IAAC bits](#) or the [Digital Crafting research](#) report by CITA.

The journal brings together research results with focus on the material research (design probes, prototypes and demonstrators). It is a durable record in which network researchers (practice and academia), ESRs and invited researchers partaking in the evaluative research events are asked to contribute with critically reflecting texts. It prepares simultaneously the basis of the reporting in the respective Deliverables of Innochain to the EU commission.

The network journal will be free of charge and be distributed electronically through issue.com. This will provide a widest possible outreach and public accessibility. It will as well have an issn number, so that it can be found and referenced through professional channels.

The network journal is published after meetings of the whole network (startup, workshop-seminars, exhibitions & colloquia) this results in an approximate 6-month rhythm of its publication.

The goal is to have an overall number of 5 network journals.

3.1.5.1 Innochain Network Journal management and protocols

A dedicated beneficiary is responsible for the network journal. The beneficiary will develop the issue in collaboration with the work package 6 lead and the network administrator and engage other ESR and partners, where needed. They organise a peer review internal to the network.

Issue	Main topic	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	Project startup, seminar, partners, participants and projects	IAAC	8
2	Workshop-seminar 1 series (1.1,1.2,1.3)	ITKE	14
3	Summerschool + First year Colloquium & Exhibition "Design Probes" The journal includes peer reviewed articles from the colloquium.	IOA	19
4	Workshop-seminar 2 series (2.1,2.2,2.3)	KTH	26
5	Second year Colloquium & Exhibition "Prototypes" The journal includes peer reviewed articles from the colloquium.	IAAC	31

3.2.6 Further Scientific dissemination activities

The Innochain network encourages members and partners to pursue further dissemination activities, such as:

- Participation in workshops
- Participation in conferences
- Books/Monographs

- Chapters in books
- Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)

The goal is that Innochain members attend 5 workshop and/or conferences per year per scientific work package.

3.2.7 General scientific Publication Protocols

Following the Grant agreements §29.2, §29.3 & §30 and the guidelines for the [Horizon 2020 Open data Pilot](#) the authors of every Innochain related scientific publication are obliged to grant open access to their **publication and the underlying datasets** and deposit them onto the central dissemination repository on www.Innochain.net. This has to take place

1. on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
2. within six months of publication in any other case.

The bibliographic metadata must be open access and identify the deposited publication. It must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms "Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions";
- the name of the action **Innochain**, acronym and grant number **642877** ;
- the **publication date**, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a [persistent identifier](#) . In case this is not granted through the publisher, the Innochain authors will take action to establish this.

The published **datasets** must furthermore be free to access and provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves).

3.3 Industry and community dissemination

Industry dissemination aims to disseminate results to the wider industry context.

The industry dissemination strategy intends to connect the network with a further partnership of strategic collaborators. This includes the invitation of high profiled individuals from industry to the networks scientific evaluation and dissemination events, such as colloquia, Pre-Viva seminars and conference, in order to strengthen the link and feedback from industry.

The use of visual media, such as video and images of Innochain events and demonstrators, supports the dissemination of eventually complex research results to an industry audience with minimal time for attention.

3.3.1 Seminars

The seminars have a strong focus on implementation and commercialisation. Linked to the hands-on workshops, the seminars invite practitioners and researchers to contextualise methods through real world examples and experimental research. The seminars are open public events and we expect an audience of experts from practice and academia.

	Workshop	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	Seminar 1.1 Communication design.	CITA	12
2	Seminar 1.2 Simulating design	ITKE	12
3	Seminar 1.3 Materialising design	BSA	12
4	Seminar 2.1 Communicating design	KTH	24
5	Seminar 2.2 Simulating design	IOA	24
6	Seminar 2.3 Materialising design	IAAC	24

3.3.1.1 Innochain seminar protocols

The organising beneficiary invites in collaboration with the network organiser through industry related channels to the event.

The organising beneficiary is responsible for the documentation on event with good quality photo and video and the publication of these over www.innochain.net and the other Innochain web platform. The seminars will be documented in the Innochain network journal.

3.3.2 Publication in industry related press

The focus on implementation is further supported by a strong interest in publishing in professional industry press, which are typically Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications). In architecture and engineering there is a strong focus on industry press as a means of knowledge sharing.

We aim to publish research findings in central industry based journals such as:

DETAIL (DE), VDI Nachrichten (DE), TEC21 (CH), Arkitekten (DK), Ingeniøren (DK), Arkitekten (SE), Betong (SE) and Architect's Journal (UK)

3.3.3 Further industry related dissemination activities

During the course of the Innochain network further activities with a focus appealing to industry will emerge, such as:

- The summerschool “Drivers of Innovation” organised and run by the Innochain industry partner HENN
- Videos (of i.e. events, demonstrators)
- Participation in Trade fairs
- Participation in industry oriented conferences (i.e. SmartGeometry)
- Press release
- Industry directed flyers and invitations for training and other Innochain events

3.3.4 General industry related dissemination protocols

Unless it is impossible or the Innochain Supervisor board agrees any industry related result and dissemination document or action must:

- Display the Innochain and EU emblem with appropriate prominence and balance to each other and eventually other displayed emblems

- Refer to the project's website URL www.Innochain.net
- show the following text:
"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 642877"

4 Appendix 1: Research exhibition plan

Innochain has planned three public exhibitions.

Exhibition	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
First year Exhibition "Design Probes"	IOA	18
Second year Exhibition "Prototypes"	KTH	30
Final exhibition "Demonstrators"	CITA	45

5 Appendix 2: Public Event Plan

This plan provides an overview of the planned activities with public participation.

5.1 Innochain Conference

The network will conclude in a large scale international conference with peer reviewed paper presentations from the field.

Conference	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
Concluding international conference	CITA	45

5.2 Innochain Workshops

The workshops are hands-on and share particular methods and tools. They provide the linked seminars with a solid base of experience to foster critical reflection.

	Workshop	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	Workshop-seminar 1.1 Communication design	CITA	12
2	Workshop-seminar 1.2 Simulating design	ITKE	12
3	Workshop-seminar 1.3 Materialising design	BSA	12
4	Workshop-seminar 2.1 Communicating design	KTH	24
5	Workshop-seminar 2.2 Simulating design	IOA	24
6	Workshop-seminar 2.3 Materialising design	IAAC	24

5.3 Innochain Seminars

The seminars have a strong focus on implementation and commercialisation. Linked to the hands-on workshops, the seminars invite practitioners and researchers to contextualise

methods through real world examples and experimental research. The seminars are open public events and we expect an audience of experts from practice and academia.

	Workshop	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	Seminar 1.1 Communication design.	CITA	12
2	Seminar 1.2 Simulating design	ITKE	12
3	Seminar 1.3 Materialising design	BSA	12
4	Seminar 2.1 Communicating design	KTH	24
5	Seminar 2.2 Simulating design	IOA	24
6	Seminar 2.3 Materialising design	IAAC	24

5.4 Further public outreach activities to local environments

The Innochain network and its members will partake in public outreach activities, such as:

- presenting research to school and A level students
- developing themed workshops with bachelor and masters students
- participating in public dissemination event such as The Festival of Research, DK, European Researchers Night (UK) and Lange Nacht der Wissenschaften (DE)

6 Appendix 3: Publication Plan

This plan provides an overview over the planned publication activities toward public, scientific and industry related target groups.

6.1 Innochain Network Journal (Public Dissemination)

The Innochain network journal aims to disseminate results to a wider audience of interested public, architecture practitioners, students and researchers alike.

A dedicated beneficiary is responsible for the network journal. The beneficiary will develop the issue in collaboration with the workpackage 6 lead and the network administrator and engage other ESR and partners, where needed.

Issue	Main topic	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	Project startup, seminar, partners, participants and projects	IAAC	8
2	Workshop-seminar 1	ITKE	14
3	Summerschool + First year Colloquium & Exhibition "Design Probes" The journal includes peer reviewed articles from the colloquium.	IOA	19
4	Workshop-seminar 2	KTH	26
5	Second year Colloquium & Exhibition "Prototypes" The journal includes peer reviewed articles from the colloquium.	IAAC	31

6.2 Extended catalogue (Public Dissemination)

The extended catalogue is issued after the final exhibition and international conference of the network. It disseminates the results to a wider audience of interested public, architecture practitioners, students and researchers alike. It is a durable record in which network researchers (practice and academia), ESRs and invited researchers partaking are asked to contribute with critically reflecting texts.

The catalogue is issued electronically and follows established formats, as the [Digital Crafting research](#) extended catalogue by CITA.

	Main topic	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	Extended Catalogue	CITA	45

6.3 Publication in international conferences, workshops and journals (Scientific Publication)

Research results will be progressively published in key international research conferences, such as:

ACADIA, Advances in Architectural Geometry, Design Modelling Symposium, RobArch, Fabricate, IASS, IABSE (international association for bridge and structural engineering) and eCAADe

and journals such as:

IJAC (International Journal of Architecture and Computation) or IJSS (International Journal of Shell and Spatial Structures)

The goal is to have three scientific publications per year per scientific workpackage in a conference, workshop or journal external to the network.

6.4 Further Scientific dissemination activities (Scientific Publication)

The Innochain network encourages members and partners to pursue further publication activities, such as:

- Books/Monographs
- Chapters in books

6.5 Publication in industry related press (Industry Publication)

The focus on implementation is further supported by a strong interest in publishing in professional industry press, which are typically Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications). In architecture and engineering there is a strong focus on industry press as a means of knowledge sharing. We aim to publish research findings in central industry based journals such as:

DETAIL (DE), VDI Nachrichten (DE), TEC21 (CH), Arkitekten (DK), Ingeniøren (DK), Arkitekten (SE), Betong (SE) and Architect's Journal (UK)